

made at harvest (see table).

Application of SBP reduced disease incidence and percentage of chaffy grains. It increased the number of panicle-bearing tillers and total yield over that in the inoculated control. However, differences among various treatments were not significant. SBP is cheaper than other spray chemicals. One or two 15 kg/ha applications during the rainy season, when it is difficult to spray the crop, may help prevent a secondary spread of the pathogen. ■

Effect of soil-applied stable bleaching powder in controlling bacterial blight of rice, av for 2 years, Ludhiana, India, 1977-78.

Applications (no.)	Disease incidence (%)	Yield (t/ha)	Wt (g) of 1000 healthy grains	Chaffiness (%)	Tillers (no./m ²)	
					With panicles	Without panicles
1	50.8	5.6	28.2	25.8	220.5	68.5
2	49.9	5.6	28.8	25.8	223.0	56.5
3	49.6	5.7	28.9	25.6	234.0	52.0
Control (inoculated)	58.9	5.0	28.8	32.7	215.5	73.5
Control (uninoculated)	9.4	6.4	29.3	15.9	272.0	45.0

A survey of South Arcot District in Tamil Nadu for diseases of rice

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India

The rice crop on about 230 ha in 8 villages (Vaniyampalayam, Sundaripalayam, V. Akaram, Kurunthipadi, Pennadam, Mazhikaikottam, Eraiyur, and Erappavur) in South Arcot district of Tamil Nadu was surveyed for rice diseases on 13 and

Disease incidence on 4 varieties of rice, Tamil Nadu, India, 1978.

Variety	Tungro (%)	Brown spot (%)	Sheath rot (%)	Narrow brown leaf spot (%)
IR20	56.3	—	43.2	29.6
BCP 1	17.9	—	11.6	3.4
Co 40	90.7	81.5	31.9	5.9
Ponni	35.2	—	17.4	—

14 December 1978. Rice tungro virus disease had the highest incidence,

followed by sheath rot and narrow brown leaf spot (see table). ■

Pest management and control INSECTS

Yield loss due to rice tungro virus

S. Srinivasan, Paddy Experiment Station (PES), Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India

During 1978 kuruvai and samba, a severe incidence of rice tungro virus was observed in Thanjavur district of Tamil Nadu. A study to estimate yield loss caused by the virus was undertaken. The test variety was the highly susceptible ADT 31. Yields from 100 hills that

Yield losses caused by rice tungro virus, Thanjavur district, India, 1978.

Time (DT) ^a when disease symptoms were observed	Grain yield (g/100 hills)	Yield loss (%)
<i>Diseased plants</i>		
15	8.8	98.5
30	14.8	97.2
45	369.6	30.4
60	490.2	7.5
<i>Healthy plants</i>		
	529.7	

^aDays after transplanting.

showed disease symptoms at 15, 30, 45, and 60 days after transplanting were recorded. The yield from 100 healthy hills was also recorded (see table).

During the year severe tungro disease reduced the yield from some of the PES fields to only 450-700 kg/ha. ■

Attraction of gall midge to lights

S. K. Shrivastava, P. D. Deshmukh, D. J. Pophali, G. A. Gangrade, U. K. Kaushik, B. C. Shukla, and G. L. Patidar. Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, College of Agriculture, Raipur, Madhya Pradesh, India

A 1978 epidemic of *Orseolia oryzae* on kharif paddy in Chattisgarh region, Madhya Pradesh, is suspected to have been caused by the fact that the summer paddy crop (Jan-Jun) was linked with the kharif season, so gall midge is carried over. About 8% of the tillers of the

preceding summer paddy crop harbored gall midge.

A 100-watt electric bulb was fitted at 2-m height near farmhouse walls at both Raipur and Marod. Swarms of gall midge adults attracted to the lights were then caught by hand net. Times of peak catches at both locations were similar. At Marod 2.1% were caught from 1800 to 1900 hours, 22.5% from 1900 to 2000, 29.8% from 2000 to 2100, 27.5% from 2100 to 2200, and 15.5% from 2200 to 2300 (Fig. 1). The majority (87.4%) of the flies were attracted between 1900 to 2300. After that, the catches declined to 8.3% just before midnight. Thus 97.8% of the flies were attracted and caught before midnight.

Peculiarly, at midnight of 29 September, 98% of the flies were attracted between 2000 and 2100 hours. That night 877,500 flies were collected (Fig. 2). Catches declined the next day. Weather conditions (evening temperature

Hourly attraction of gall midge to electric bulb, Tamil Nadu, India.

Hourly collection of gall midge by light. Tamil Nadu, India.

and humidity) caused the wide fluctuations in fly attraction. The sex ratio of males to females was about 1:7.

Electric lights were a powerful attraction for gall midge and may be useful in integrated control. But unlike ordinary lamps and the Petromax lamp, they do not kill the flies. Electric lights designed to kill flies would greatly reduce the gall midge population. ■

Fumigation effect of certain granular insecticides against the brown planthopper

P. R. M. Rao and P. S. Prakasa Rao, Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, Orissa, India

Certain insecticides used either as foliar spray or as paddy water application act as fumigants, and, at least initially, give considerable control. This finding may be significant for brown planthopper (BPH) control because most of the adults and nymphs stay at the base of the rice plants. When applied to paddy water or as foliar spray, insecticides that have high fumigant action may be more effective in the field, considering that the thick rice canopy forms an air cover for this special microhabitat.

Sixteen commercial granular insecticides at 1.5 kg a.i./ha in wet and dry forms were tested against BPH adults. Dry granules and granules moistened with water were tested separately in an experiment replicated three times. The required amount of each insecticide

Evaluation of insecticides applied at 1.5 kg a.i./ha in wet and dry forms for their effectiveness as fumigants against brown planthopper adults.^a 11-14 Apr 1977, CRRI, India.

Insecticide	Corrected mortality (%) of insects exposed			
	12 h		24 h	
	Dry form	Wet form	Dry form	Wet form
Phorate	100	100	100	100
AC92, 100 (Counter)	100	100	100	100
BPMC	50	100	100	100
MIX	30	10	77	70
Disulfoton	73	30	100	60
Endosulfan + BPMC	40	30	70	57
Fenthion	0	17	13	40
Fensulfothion	0	10	0	13
Quinalphos	0	3	7	10
Carbofuran	0	0	33	0
Chlordimeform	20	0	37	0
Monocrotophos	0	0	0	0
Lindane	0	0	0	0
Fenitrothion	0	10	10	23
SAN 197	13	3	27	23
SAN 1551	0	0	10	23
Control	0	0	0	0

^a Max temp = 34.4°C, min temp = 22.2°C, mean max temp = 33.7°C, mean min temp = 24.3°C, mean RH = 74%.

(calculated on the basis of the diameter of the chimney used in the investigations) was kept in small cups, over which a fine wire mesh (36 gauze) was placed to

prevent BPH from coming in direct contact with the chemicals. The small cups were kept near the base of potted plants of TN1 and a chimney covered